

MIGRANT REMITTANCES AND EXCHANGE RATE DYNAMICS IN TÜRKİYE AND SELECTED EASTERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of migrant remittances on exchange rate dynamics in Türkiye and selected Eastern European countries (Romania and North Macedonia). Globalization and international migration movements affect economic balances through migrants sending their earnings back to their home countries. Exchange rate fluctuations are a decisive factor in both the financial well-being of migrants and the amount of money they send. This article analyses the interaction between migrant remittances and exchange rates, revealing how structural differences across countries shape the trajectory of this relationship. The challenges Türkiye faces in attracting migrant remittances and the more stable exchange rate policies of countries such as Romania and North Macedonia are examined from a comparative perspective. The findings suggest that exchange rate volatility can increase economic vulnerabilities, but with appropriate policy frameworks, migrant remittances can contribute to sustainable development.

Keywords: remittances, exchange rate, migration economics, Dutch Disease

Introduction

Globalization is understood as the increasing interconnectedness of countries and their populations as a result of significant reductions in transportation and communication costs, along with the removal of artificial barriers to the movement of goods, services, capital, knowledge, and (to a more limited extent) people across countries, leading to various positive and negative effects at both the macroeconomic and microeconomic level. [1] While international migration in the field of social sciences is largely traced back to the Industrial Revolution, it was greatly shaped by the two World Wars in the twentieth century. The rising labor needs of industrial nations further fueled migration flows from rural regions to cities and from underdeveloped sectors to highly developed industries. These shifts brought about a range of social, cultural, and economic effects and implications. [2]

Exchange rates impact migrants' economic well-being by influencing the value of remittances they send home. A favorable exchange rate can boost the purchasing power of remittances, allowing migrants to sustain their families and invest in local enterprises. [3] Unfavorable exchange rates, on the other hand, might diminish the value of remittances, discouraging migration and harming the sending country's socioeconomic growth.

Furthermore, fluctuations in exchange rates might have an impact on migration decisions by changing the cost of living in different countries. For example, a currency depreciation in the host nation may diminish migrants' actual income, prompting people to return to their home countries or seek possibilities in other countries with more favorable economic conditions. [4] This connection between currency rates and migration patterns needs a thorough investigation of the influence of economic policy and global financial markets on migration.

The influence of exchange rates on migration is an important scientific issue, particularly in emerging

economies. Exchange rate fluctuations have a direct impact on economic aspects such as migrants' work options, income creation, and money sent home (migrant remittances). It may result in both positive and bad results. Among the positive implications is an increase in the value of the money migrants send to their family as exchange rates rise, which can help those families' living conditions. Exchange rate swings, on the other hand, might have a detrimental impact on migrants' job search procedures and income, complicating their economic condition. [5]

The aim of this study is to analyze the impact of migrant remittances on exchange rates in Türkiye and selected Eastern European countries (Romania and North Macedonia), and to examine how this relationship manifests differently across these regions. This study contributes to the literature by offering a comparative perspective on remittance-driven exchange rate dynamics between a large emerging economy and smaller transition economies. Its originality lies in highlighting how structural differences in exchange rate regimes and remittance volatility shape economic vulnerability and policy needs.

Literature Review

There are many studies in the literature on the effects of exchange rates on the economic situation of migrants. For example, [6] examined the effects of migrant remittances on the real exchange rate and noted that this situation had a positive impact on economic growth in recipient countries. However, they also emphasized that an increase in exchange rates could have a negative impact on the external trade balances of recipient countries.

The impact of exchange rates on migration is generally examined through two main mechanisms: economic costs and income expectations. [7] argue that fluctuations in exchange rates can affect migrants' reservation wages and career paths in the host country. In their study, they noted that individuals migrating to Germany started with lower wages due to exchange rate

advantages, but these wages increased over time. [8] examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on migrants' remittances using the example of Pakistan and emphasized that exchange rate stability is critical for the continuity of remittance flows. This highlights the strong economic ties between migrants and their home countries, as migrants send a significant portion of their earnings to the country where they work back to their home countries. In the case of Nigeria, [9] found that changes in exchange rates affected remittance flows in both directions and that this effect interacted with macroeconomic variables such as inflation.

Remittances play an important role as an intermediary mechanism in the relationship between exchange rates and migration. [10] examine the long- and short-term dynamics between the nominal volume of migrant remittances from the United States to Mexico and the nominal Peso-Dollar exchange rate. Using monthly data from January 1987 to December 2008, the relationships between the variables were analyzed using standard cointegration methods. The study found that the effect of exchange rate changes on remittances is more pronounced in the long term, while in the short term, there are two-way positive feedback effects between the two variables. It was concluded that Mexico could regulate its exchange rate policies to encourage remittance inflows and achieve economic gains without fear of negative effects such as Dutch Disease. The study by [11] examines the effects of migrant remittances on the real effective exchange rate and whether these effects cause Dutch disease in developing countries. The study presents an analysis covering China, Nigeria, India, Mexico, the Philippines, and other leading remittance-

receiving countries using data from 1982 to 2015. According to the results of the panel data analysis, it was observed that remittances caused the real exchange rate to appreciate in China and Nigeria but did not create a Dutch disease effect. In other countries, it was found that migrant remittances could cause economic imbalances by limiting the movement of resources in trade-related sectors. The study emphasizes the importance of directing migrant remittances to productive sectors in order to prevent the effects of Dutch disease. [5] investigated the effect of worker remittances on the equilibrium real exchange rate in Bangladesh. For this purpose, annual data from Bangladesh for the period 1980-2018 and the Johansen cointegration technique and vector error correction model (VECM) were used to estimate the relationship. The study found that fluctuations in exchange rates have an impact on the economic competitiveness of remittance flows. It was determined that these effects vary depending on countries' trade balances and employment conditions

One of the most important issues in migration literature is the network connections of migrants. In his study, [12] discusses the effect of migrants' economic networks and exchange rate fluctuations on their motivation to migrate. According to this, it has been observed that increases in exchange rates increase the tendency of individuals with less connected social networks to migrate.

Comparative Empirical Background

The comparison of Türkiye and selected Eastern European countries in terms of the exchange rate-workers' remittances relationship is presented in the table below:

Table 1
Exchange Rate Volatility and the Dutch Disease Risk in Türkiye, Romania, and North Macedonia (2010–2020)

Country	De Jure Exchange Rate Regime	Average Remittances / GDP (%)	Real Exchange Rate Volatility (Standard Deviation)	Dutch Disease Find
Türkiye	Free Floating	0.1836	High	Limited effects
Romania	Managed Floating	2,4744	Low	Potential effects
North Macedonia	Fixed	3.6199	Low	Potential effects

Source: [13],[14]

Discussion

Remittance flows in nations with significant exchange rate volatility, such as Türkiye, are more irregular and typically impacted by short-term economic choices and external shocks. Thus, Turkish-originated people especially living and working in European countries like Germany and France, are not willing to transfer their remittances to Türkiye for investment. In contrast, in Eastern European nations such as Romania and Bulgaria, remittances have matured into more reliable and dependable sources of external financing. These nations have successfully institutionalized remittance inflows, using them to promote social policies and plan economic development.

Türkiye's experience suggests that remittances should be more strategically integrated into the country's macroeconomic framework. Lessons can be

learned from Eastern European countries that have established systematic approaches to channel remittance funds into productive areas such as education, infrastructure, and entrepreneurship. In this sense, expatriates in Europe can be encouraged. By failing to incorporate remittances into a comprehensive development plan, Turkey may be underutilizing a powerful tool for economic resilience and inclusive growth. A comparative policy study indicates that the volatility of remittance inflows in Turkey could be reduced through targeted incentives, financial literacy initiatives, and diaspora engagement policies. These strategies are becoming increasingly common in the policy frameworks of Romania and Bulgaria.

While all three countries receive substantial remittance inflows, the risk of Dutch Disease varies due to

differences in economic structure and exchange rate regimes. In Türkiye, the relatively lower share of remittances in GDP and a more diversified export base reduce the likelihood of significant real exchange rate appreciation driven by remittances. However, periodic currency crises may amplify short-term distortions. In contrast, Romania and North Macedonia, where remittances represent a larger portion of GDP, face a more pronounced risk of Dutch Disease, particularly when inflows lead to sustained currency appreciation without corresponding increases in productivity.

Conclusion

Remittances sent by migrant workers constitute an important source of external financing for developing countries. However, certain macroeconomic variables can adversely affect these flows. Exchange rate volatility is one of these key factors. Despite the large population of Turkish-origin individuals living in Europe, Türkiye has not been able to attract sufficient remittance inflows. One of the main reasons for this is the instability in the exchange rate and the broader economy. Due to its large economy and diversified external financing sources, Türkiye does not strongly experience the Dutch Disease effect commonly discussed in the literature. In contrast, countries like North Macedonia and Romania, which rely more heavily on remittances as a share of their GDP, are more likely to be affected by Dutch Disease. In this regard, Türkiye should adopt policies similar to those of Eastern European countries to increase remittance inflows and channel them into productive sectors.

References

1. Stiglitz, J. E. (2002). *Globalization and its discontents*. W. W. Norton & Company.
2. Görgün, M. (2017). The importance of migrant social networks in the process of globalization. *Süleyman Demirel University The Journal of Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, Vol. 22, pp. 1317-1327.
3. Lianos, T. P. (2018). Migration and remittances: Economic impacts and future perspectives. In *International Migration* (pp. 105-120). Springer.
4. Massey, D. S., Arango, J., Hugo, G., Kouaouci, A., Pellegrino, A., & Taylor, J. E. (1994). An evaluation of international migration theory: The North American case. *Population and Development Review*, 20(4), 699-751.
5. Dhar, Z. (2018). Nexus between Remittance and the Real Exchange Rate: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Rajshahi University Journal of Social Science and Business Studies*, 26, 57-69.
6. Amuedo-Dorantes, C., & Pozo, S. (2004). Workers' remittances and the real exchange rate: A paradox of gifts. *World Development*, 32(8), 1407-1417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2004.02.004>
7. Dustmann, C., Ku, H., & Surovtseva, T. (2021). Real Exchange Rates and the Earnings of Immigrants. *Centre for Research and Analysis of Migration*.
8. Munir, K., & Riaz, N. (2021). Remittances-Exchange Rate Nexus: Evidence from Pakistan. *Audit and Accounting Review*.
9. Orekoya, S., & Akintunde, O. (2023). Examining Inflation, Exchange Rate and Remittance Inflow Nexus in Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social Issues*.
10. Rahman, M., Foshee, A., & Mustafa, M. (2013). Remittances—Exchange Rate Nexus: The U.S.—Mexico Case. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 47(1), 63-74. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jda.2013.0000>
11. Üçler, G., & Özşahin, Ş. (2017). Göçmen Gönderileri ve Reel Efektif Döviz Kuru İlişkisi: Gelişmekte Olan Ülkelerde Hollanda Hastalığı Etkisi Üzerine Ampirik Bir Analiz. *Turkish Studies*, 12(24), 215-240.
12. Hersey, T. (2024). Migration, Networks, and Religious Choice. *Job Market Paper*.
13. TradingEconomics.com (remittance inflows to GDP data for Türkiye, Romania, and North Macedonia 2010-2020).
14. IMF Working Paper (2017). Exchange Rate Regimes in Central, Eastern, and Southeastern Europe: A Euro Bloc and a Dollar Bloc? WP/17/83.